

A new record for the flora of Bangladesh: *Oxyspora paniculata* (D. Don) DC. (Melastomataceae)

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Abstract

Oxyspora paniculata was found in Hazarikhil Wildlife Sanctuary of Bangladesh that represents a new record to the flora of the country. The species has been described with photographs.

The family Melastomataceae includes 4000 species and 200 genera around the world (Ahmed et al., 2009). Among these genera, the *Oxyspora* genus comprises six species (The Plant List, 2013). Two species of *Oxyspora* genus are already listed in Bangladesh. *Oxyspora paniculata* (see <http://www.ipni.org/ipni/idPlantNameSearch.do?id=574548-1>) was not reported in the relevant literatures (Ahmed et al., 2009; Pasha & Uddin, 2013; Rahman & Hassan, 2017), therefore, this species (Figure 1) is reported here for the first time from Bangladesh. Specimens (n=2) of species were collected from Kalapainna Chora, Hazarikhil Wildlife Sanctuary, Harualchari, Vuzpur, Fatikchari, Chittagong, Bangladesh (Latitude: 22.709089, Longitude: 91.692842). The photographs of species in natural habitat were taken during the field trip. The collected specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of Chittagong University (HCU). Those specimens were identified and described by consulting floristic literatures and databases (e.g., Ahmed et al., 2009; Airy-Shaw, 1966; Flora of China, 2018; Flowers of India, 2016; Pasha & Uddin, 2013; Prain, 1903; Rahman & Uddin, 1997; Rahman & Hassan, 2017; Roxburgh, 1814).

Our newly reported species can be characterized by a shrub with spreading, drooping branches. Stems 4-sided to obtusely 4-sided, furfuraceous stellate and sparsely puberulous-setose. Leaves petiolate, densely furfuraceous stellate; leaf blade ovate, narrowly elliptic-acute, stiffly papery, abaxially usually furfuraceous stellate on veins, adaxially furfuraceous squamose or glabrescent, secondary veins 2 on each side of mid-vein, base rounded to subcordate, margin denticulate, apex

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Figure 1. *Oxyspora paniculata* collected from Hazarikhil Wildlife Sanctuary, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

(a, b) Plants in natural habitat. (c) Inflorescence of *Oxyspora paniculata*.

acuminate. Inflorescences terminal, a cymose panicle, furfuraceous stellate, with 2 leaflike bracts at base. Bractlets and bracteole lanceolate to subulate. Hypanthium narrowly funnel formed, longitudinally 8-ribbed, with dense stellate trichomes when young but glabrescent. Calyx lobes shortly triangular-ovate, apex acute and apiculate. Petals pinkish-purple, elliptic and fall soon. Stamens 8 in number, with 4 longer with curved filaments and purple anthers, and 4 shorter with yellow anthers. Style simple, elongate. Fruit capsulated, obovoid; hypanthium narrowly funnel formed.

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